

A Geographic Analysis of the Agriculture Development within Bago Township

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Abstract

This research paper identifies the present condition of agricultural development in Bago Township. Since agricultural development is primarily depends on such physical factors as relief, climate and soils relationship between these factors and the possibility of agricultural intensification is explored. To indentified the agricultural intensity of the study area, horizontal expansion, vertical expansion which indicates multiple cropping converage as well as cropping intensity are analyzed together with the major crops grown and their land holding capacity, using essentially secondary data and relevant statistical method and illustrating with maps and diagram.

Introduction

Bago with its vast tract of productive agricultural hinterland was once the capacity city of Mon and Myanmar Kings for several centuries. Even as a township unit in the modern time, it occupies about two-third of the low flatland for field crops and extensive foot-slopes for perennial crops and township economy rest largely on agriculture. With the adoption of open market economic system and the extended use of water resources for irrigation, agricultural intensity of the township has improved noticeable in the recent year. In order to have deeper insight of the development level and momentum of agricultural activities, the title is chosen to conduct a research work from the geographical standpoint.

Objectives

1. To examine the basic physical geographic factors favorable for agriculture.
2. To assess the development level of agriculture with relevant indicators
3. To seek out means for further development

Methodology

The collected office or secondary data are analyzed by sample statistical method in measuring the level of agricultueal development. Comparatively study is conducted to highlight conditions of agricultural achievement relative to other township within Bago Division. Field survey and open talk with several cultivators are carried out to verify the collected data. Map and diagram are used for illustration.

Location, size and shape

Bago Township lies between the Ayeyarwady deltaic region and Sittaung river valley, occupying the Bago river and mountain spurs of Bago Yoma. It extends from latitudes 17°04' to 17°50' N and from longitudes 94°41'E to 96°41'E. It is about 50 miles by motor road and 45 miles by railroad to Yangon City. Bago Township bordered by Letpadan and Kyanktaga townships in the north, Daik-U, Waw and Tanatpin Township in the east, Kawa Township in the south, and Hlegu, Taikkyi and Thayarwady Township in the west. It has locational

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advantages for agriculture being occupied the broad tract of the low fertile plain built by the Bago River and its tributaries and accessible easily to Yangon City as well as other parts of the country.

The area of Bago Township is 2905.09 square kilometers (1121.66 square miles), ranking first in size among the 28 townships of Bago Region. It is made up of 68 village tracts in the rural area and 31 wards in the urban area. The names of the village tracts and wards are shown in Figure (3), (4).

Bago Township has roughly a distorted rectangular shape with an extreme length of 71 miles from north to south and an extreme width of 30 miles from east to west.

1.2. Relief and Drainage

The distinctive features of the area are the low hills and mountain spurs of Bago Yoma in the north and the low alluvial plain in the middle and south. Between these two distinct landforms lies the traditional zone with elevation between 250 feet and 500 feet above sea-level.

The hilly region of the north occupies nearly one-third of the township area. In the northwestern margin the elevation is a little over 2000 feet and the Kantbalu Mountain is the higher part of the north which is more suitable to keep as forestland than converting it into agricultural land. The transitional zone is uneven, but it is suitable for growing perennial crops like rubber and cashew.

The alluvial plain formed by the Bago River and its tributaries is fairly extensive covering about two-thirds of the township area. The elevation along the northern margin is about 250 feet. The southern half of the township, in fact, is below 50 feet and the land is extremely flat which serves as the ideal medium for growing field crops, especially paddy and pulses. The agricultural development potential is largely related to the presence of this low alluvial plain.

Drainage

The chief drainage is the Bago River system which drains through the township from north to south. A number of streams that take their sources from the west, north and east join the Bago River. Owing to sharp slope gradient, the stream lines rush down the slopes in the rainy season causing Bago River flood. The frequency and magnitude of floods sharply reduce after the construction of Zaungtu Irrigation. Hydro Power Project, The relatively larger tributaries that join the Bago River from the east are Sinswe, Theedaw, Dawei, Kodukwe, Shwelaung and Salu and that join from the west are Htantawgyi and Zalathtaw. Some of these streams serve as irrigation source for the cultivation of crops in the dry season. The existing streams combined with heavy rain enhance the frequency of floods which cause damage of planted crops, but on the hand they support the expansion of multiple cropping area through irrigation, in addition to being used as waterways for local transport in the wet season Fig (5).

1.3. Climate

Climate factors, especially amount of rainfall and time of precipitation are important for the cultivation of crops, since the area falls within the tropics, the temperatures are high throughout the years except a few months in the winter. Based on the coldest mean monthly temperature and the mean annual rainfall, the climate type of the study area is Tropical Monsoon(Am), characterized by alternate wet and dry periods. The climate has three distinct seasons, rainy season from the third week of May to the end of October, the cold season from November to the end of February and the hot dry season from December to the second week of May. The seasonal rain is favourable for the cultivation of different crops, paddy, sesamum, and crops that thrive on flooded fields or under heavy rain in the rainy season, and groundnut and pulses in the early dry season (winter). Crops need water in high in the hot dry season and thus cropping is impossible without irrigation.

Table (1) Normal Temperature of Bago (1974-2009)

Temperature	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Maximum Temp: (C°)	31.50	33.70	36.40	37.50	34.80	30.50	29.90	29.40	30.80	32.10	32.10	30.70
Maximum Temp: (F°)	88.70	92.66	97.52	99.50	94.64	86.90	85.82	84.92	87.44	89.78	89.78	87.26
Minimum Temp: (C°)	16.00	16.90	20.50	23.50	24.30	23.50	23.60	23.50	23.70	23.10	20.90	16.70
Minimum Temp: (F°)	60.80	62.64	68.90	74.30	75.74	74.30	74.48	74.30	74.66	73.58	69.62	62.06
Mean Temp : (C°)	23.70	25.30	28.40	30.50	29.50	27.00	26.40	26.70	27.20	27.60	26.50	23.70
Mean Temp: (F°)	74.66	77.54	85.12	86.90	85.10	80.60	79.52	80.06	80.96	81.68	79.70	74.66

Table(2) Normal Rainfall and Rainy Days of Bago (1974-2009)

Station	Total	Rainfall	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Bago	30	Rainfall	0.20	0.28	0.30	1.53	12.58	24.87	30.38	29.79	19.62	7.70	2.07	0.37	129.68
		Rainy	0.30	0.30	0.40	2.00	13.70	24.60	27.50	27.00	21.30	10.30	2.09	0.50	129.99

Source: Meteorology and Hydrology Department, Yangon.

As temperature is high all year round, it has no adverse effect on the plant growth. However, high temperature in the hot dry season enhances the rate of evaporation and evapotranspiration and soil moisture deficit occurs during these months.

The mean annual rainfall is 3548mm (139.67 inches). Heavy rain in June, July and August occasionally causes widespread flooding which damages the planted crops Table (1)(2) and Fig (6).

1.4 Soils

Soil types vary depending on relief, drainage, climate, vegetation and parent material. The most common soil types are classified as follows:

- (1) Meadow alluvial soils
- (2) Meadow gray soils
- (3) Swampy soils
- (4) Turfy primitive soils
- (5) Yellow brown forest soils

Meadow gray soils occupy the eastern area of the Bago River from Htonegyi Village in the north to the Lagunpyin Creek in the south. With fairly high fertility, the soil is well suited to growing paddy in the rainy season and pulses in the early dry season. Meadow alluvial soils are confined to along the streams are also favourable for growing paddy, tobacco and vegetables. Swampy soils develop around Moeyungyi wetland which can also be used as paddy land. Yellow brown forest soils occupy about 60 percent of the Township area. The summits of mountain spurs are covered with turfy primitive soils mostly under forest.

Generally, much of the existing soils are favourable for growing field crops as well as perennial crops Fig(7).

1.5. Natural Vegetation

As the study area is within the tropics with high temperature all year round and a total annual rainfall of more than 100 inches much of the study area might have been covered with thick forests. Although much of the forests in the low land area have been removed, three still remains as wide tract of forests in the upland area. These forests can be classified as:

- (1) Tropical evergreen forests
- (2) mixed deciduous forest and
- (3) indaing forests.

CHAPTER II

Major Types of Land Use

2.1. Cultivated land

The average cultivated land area in the 10-year period from 2005-2006 to 2014-2015 was 201236.5 acres, representing 28.03 percent of the township area. Among the different types of cultivation, Le land ranks first in acreage, followed by Kaing-Kyun and garden lands. Dhani land is the least in area.

2.1.1. Type of Agriculture

2.1.1.1 Le Land

Agriculture is the most significant economic activity in Bago Township. To boost the agricultural produces, the government has been providing assistance to the individual farmers and organization as well. Generally there are two types of Le land, highly fertile land and moderately fertile land. Highly fertile land occupies the southern and northeastern part of the township, covered with gray soil which is highly suitable for growing paddy. However, in some places of there area, the drainage is moderately poor to poor, causing the land inundated for more than six months. The lands with moderately fertile soil and found on both sides of the Bago River except the southern channel section and in area to the east of the Bago River. This type of le land can be modified to boost the crops production by applying more fertilizers practicing scientific farming methods and using improved quality seeds.

The average 'Le' land area in the 10-year period was 103347.4 acres which accounted for 51.32 percent of the cultivated land.

2.1.1.2. Kaing- Kyun land

Kaing –Kyun land occurs along the narrow belt of the Bago valley. During the period from 2005-2006 to 2014-2015, it averaged 4471.2 areas, accounting for 2.21 perecent of the total occupied area. The area kept as fallow has been decreasing as the prices of groundnut, maize, chili, sunflower and vegetable have been increasing. The most dominant crop grown on Kaing land is groundnut.

Table (3) The General land use of Bago Township

Cultivated Land		Reserved Forest	Waste	Uncultivated Land		Total Area
Le	108969	396046	7081	Pasture	5289	
Kaing	5970			Railroad land	949	
Gerden	93238			Road land	3738	
Dhani	39			Dam, ponds reservoir land	3863	
				Stream and underwater land	16265	
				In the lake land	2624	
				Plants and factory land	1362	
				Urban settlement land	12201	
				Rural settlement land	5482	
				Airfield	9842	
				Religions, cemetry and	34268	
				Unclassified land	10635	
Total	208216	396046	7081		106518	717861

Fig. 8. GENERAL LAND USE OF BAGO TOWNSHIP

Table (4) Cultivated Lands of Bago Township

Year	Le-Land		Kaing Land		Garden Land		Dhani Land		Total		Net sown
	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	
2005-2006	109636	55.4	406	2.0	112966	57.1	39	0.01	226706	87.22	197748
2006-2007	108222	55.0	406	2.0	113525	57.7	39	0.01	225852	114.9	196418
2007-2008	107738	54.7	406	2.0	114092	57.9	39	0.01	225934	114.7	196923
2008-2009	107935	54.8	406	2.0	115292	58.5	39	0.01	227331	115.5	196768
2009-2010	107935	54.4	406	2.0	115292	58.1	39	0.01	227331	114.6	198264
2010-2011	122133	61.9	404	2.0	115651	58.6	39	0.01	241870	122.5	197299
2011-2012	122133	59.3	404	1.9	115651	56.2	39	0.01	241870	117.5	205696
2012-2013	122869	59.3	517	2.5	115751	55.9	39	0.01	243838	117.7	207067
2013-2014	125098	60.1	607	2.9	115753	55.6	39	0.01	246968	118.7	207966
2014-2015	125391	60.2	607	2.9	116655	56.0	39	0.01	248163	119.1	2008216
Average	115909	57.5	4575	2.2	103533	51.4	39	0.01	235586	117.0	201236

Sources: Land Records Department in Bago Township

Fig. 9. TYPES OF AGRICULTURAL LAND IN BAGO TOWNSHIP

Table (5) The Conditions of net sown area in Bago Township (2006-2015)

Year	Le-Land		Kaing Land		Garden Land		Dhani Land		Net sown acreage
	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	
2005-2006	99694	50.41	3957	2.00	94058	47.56	39	0.01	197748
2006-2007	99224	50.51	3957	2.01	93198	47.44	39	0.01	196418
2007-2008	99425	50.48	3957	2.00	93502	47.48	39	0.01	196418
2008-2009	99311	50.47	3957	2.01	93480	47.50	39	0.01	196718
2009-2010	100686	50.87	3957	1.99	93400	47.10	39	0.01	198264
2010-2011	100065	50.71	3957	2.00	93238	47.25	39	0.01	197299
2011-2012	108480	52.73	3957	2.92	93238	45.82	39	0.01	205696
2012-2013	108719	52.50	3957	2.44	93238	45.02	39	0.01	207067
2013-2014	108719	52.27	3957	2.87	93238	44.83	39	0.01	207966
2014-2015	108969	52.33	3957	2.86	93238	44.77	39	0.01	208216
Average	103347.4	51.32	4471.2	2.21	93382.8	46.40	39	0.01	201236.5

Sources: Land Records Department in Bago Township

Table (6) The Conditions of Fallow Land in Bago Township (2006-2015)

Year	Le-Land		Kaing Land		Garden Land		Dhani Land		Cultivated Land
	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	Acre	%	
2005-2006	9942	24.33	108	.37	18908	65.29	28958	12.77	226706
2006-2007	8998	30.57	108	.36	20327	69.06	29433	13.03	225851
2007-2008	8313	28.56	108	.37	20590	70.97	29011	12.84	225934
2008-2009	8624	28.23	108	.35	21812	71.41	30544	13.45	227331
2009-2010	7067	24.13	108	.37	21892	75.31	29067	12.78	227331
2010-2011	22068	49.51	90	.2	22413	50.28	44571	18.42	241870
2011-2012	13653	37.76	88	.24	22413	61.99	36154	14.94	241870
2012-2013	14150	38.48	108	.29	22413	61.22	36771	15.08	243838
2013-2014	16379	41.99	108	.28	22413	57.73	39002	15.79	246968
2014-2015	16422	41.11	108	.27	22413	58.62	39947	16.09	248163
Average	1256.6	35.49	108	0.31	21680	9.2	34345.8	14.51	23558612

Source: Land Records Department in Bago Township

Fig. 10. NET SOWN AREA AND FALLOW LAND IN BAGO TOWNSHIP

2.1.1.3. Garden Land

In acreage, garden land ranks second among the different types of cultivated land. These land plots occupy the lateritic mountain spurs, hills and footslopes of the Bago Yoma in the northern part of the township. These land plots are more common along the both sides of Bago-Yangon road, Intagaw and in the northeast of Htonegyi Yangon road. The average garden land area in the period from 2005-2006 to 2014-2015 was 93382.8 acres showing 46 percent of the total occupied area. The increase in the garden land area is due to the existence of vast vacant and waste land, the rising prices of garden crops, relatively high long-term benefit, the possibility of carrying out both the framework and gardening, to invest in the perennial crops, especially rubber. The village tracts that have large that have large acreage of garden land are Blue-inn, Thayargone, inntagaw, Hotongyi, Kyanktan and Htanpinchaung. The most common crops grown on the garden land are rubber, sugarcane, coffee, betal-nut coconut, plantain pineapple, custard-apple, tamarind and vegetables.

2.1.1.4 Dhani land

There is a very limited dhani land Bago Township. It is confined to along the Bago River in Ngetpawdaw and Hmawlon village tracts. The average area of dhani land in the 10-year period was only 39 acres.

2.2. Forest Land

The high temperature throughout the year and an annual rainfall of over 100 inches combined with elevated land have enhanced the growth of large forests. However, along time of human settlements and the conversion of the forestlands into agricultural land have reduced the area occupied by forests. Now forests are found only in the reserved and protected area occupied by forests. Now forests are found only in the reserved and protected area on the mountain spurs of the BagoYoma. The reserved forests and the non-reserved protected forests are North Zarmani Reserve (4928 acres), South Zarmani Reserve (196732 acres), Shwelaung-Kodukwe (54109 acres), Salu (63624 acres), Letpan-Aungmya (17112 acres), pyinma (13209 acres), Talainhma (13145 acres), Inntagaw (18692 acres), Kandawgyi (1453 acres) and Moeyungyi wildlife Sanctuary (13542 acres), totaling (396046 acres) and covering 55% of the total township area.

The forests provide the local inhabitants with foods, timber, bamboo, firewood and medicinal plants. The presence of forests helps regulate the local climatic condition, protects soil erosion, flooding and bank collapse and reduces the deposition of sediments in the stream channel and thus enhances the agriculture development.

2.3 Fallow Land

The keeping of fallow land is related to being unable to grow paddy in time in the depressed areas due to heavy rain, widespread flooding which causes damage to paddy nurseries, drought during the planting period and insufficiency of agricultural implement. Some parts of fallow land are covered with thick "Kaing " and "Kyu" Species and even large tree occupy in places.

2.4 Cultivable waste land

The cultivable waste land are generally found in the village tracts that have extensive cultivated land. Such land exists in some parts of the reserved and protected area and on slightly steeper mountain slopes. The area of the cultivable wastw land amounts to 7081 acres (2014-2015) or 0.98% of the total area of the township.

2.5 Unculturable Waste land

Fallow lands include the land left uncultivated for one or several years, but the township has no land that cannot be modified or grown certain crops.(Table 3,4,5)

CHAPTER (III)

Development of Agericulture

3.1 Horizontal Expansion of Agriculture land

The rapid increace in the number of population and the slow pace of industrialization make the local people more dependent on agriculture to earn their living. As such, the long-term fallow land and culturable waste land are coverted into agricultural land. During the 10-year period from 2005-06 to 2014-15, except dhani land, all other types of cultivated land have increased in area. In 2005-06, the area of [Le} was 109636 acres and it increased to 125391

acres in 2014-15. The increased was by 15755 acres (14.3%). The Kaing-Kyun land area also increased from 4065 acres 2005-06 to 2014-15 in 6078 acres. The increased to 116655 acres in 2014-15. The increase in the 10-years period was 3689 acres or 3.2%.

3.1.1 Expansion by Types of crops

In the past, paddy was the only dominant crop grown within the study area. Summer paddy, pluses particularly pedisein (green gram) and matpe (black gram) have been grown extensively in the recen years, having access to foreign market and high profitability.

3.2 Vertical Expansion of Cultivated Area

Vertical expansion, in fact, is the cultivation of crops on the same plots after the first crop has been harvested, and in other words, it implies to multiple cropping practice. Vertical expansion of cultivated area has increased rapidly with the rising demand for pluses which in more profit to the farmers.

3.2.1 Multiple and Mixed Cropping

Double cropping partices include growing the same crop twice because of the failure of the first crop, growing one kind of crop in early monsoon and another in the mid-monsoon period, first crop in the mid-monsoon period and second crop in the winter, and first crop in early monsoon and second in the winter. As show in Table (8). Paddy, groundnut, sesame, pulses, general food crops, vegetables are grown two times on the plot.

Table (7)The Multiple cropping Area and Mixed Cropping Area in Bago Township

Year	Multiple cropping Area (acre)	Mixed cropping Area (acre)
2005-2006	33040	7180
2006-2007	39731	5267
2007-2008	43726	5773
2008-2009	46628	7276
2009-2010	52771	7360
2010-2011	58056	12256
2011-2012	63581	13398
2012-2013	64157	40363
2013-2014	64283	48829
2014-2015	70459	51776

Source: Land Record Department in Bago Township

Table (8) The Multiple cropping Area of Bago Township (2014-2015)

No	Multiple crop	Total Acreage
1	Paddy (summer)	20341
2	groundnut (winter)	6500
3	Sesame	3111
4	Pulses	29629
5	Vegetable	10304
6	other crops	574
	Total	70459

Source: Land Record Department in Bago Township

Table (9) The mixed cropping area of Bago Township (2014-2015)

No	Mixed crop	Total Acreage
1	Corn	102
2	Sun-Flower	3500
3	Sesame (Pan-hnan)	20
4	Other oil-seed crops	4910
5	Rubber	6351
6	Fruit	5678
7	Castor	31215
	Total	51776

Source: L.R.D

The double cropped area in 2005-2006 was 33040 acres and it gradually increased to 70459 acres in 2014-2015. The average double cropped area 10-year period was 53643.2 acres which accounted for 26.656% of total occupied area. In 2014-2015, paddy, winter groundnut, pulses and sesame were grown mostly more than once.

The mixed cropped area is presented in Table (7). It was lowest in 2006-2007 with 5267 acres and highest in 2014-2015 with 51776 acres. Maize, Sunflower, sesame, other oil-seed, crops, rubber. Fruit trees and castor are mostly grown as mixed crops. Usually the areas under mixed crops increase in the winter. The mixed crops and their respective sown acreages are presented in Table (9).

3.2.2 Irrigated Cropping

Although the study area receives an annual rainfall of more than 100 inches. Summer paddy, summer sesame and pulses are the chief crops grown with irrigation water. The irrigated cropped area has increased from 27005 acres in 2005-2006 to 35126 acres in 2014-2015 which accounted for 14.15 percent of the total occupied area. Summer paddy shared 68098 percent of the irrigated area. Phayarkalay, Pyinbon and Wunbaeinn village tracts receive

water from Moeyungyi Inn and Sainthi and Auksiti (East) village tracts from the Bago-Sittaung canal. Shwetan, Molkala, Auksiti (East) village tracts acquire water by blocking nearby streams by digging irrigation canals. Now the construction of Mazin Dam has been completed and more irrigation water will be available from this source within the study area. Irrigation canals are also dug in Kali, Bantbwegone, Shanywagyi, Lagunpyin and Kyaikkay village tracts. The dam and irrigation canal not only reduce the frequency and magnitude of floods, but also enhance the irrigated farming.

3.2.3 Cropping Intensity

Cropping intensity is generally used as one of the measures for agricultural intensity of the given area. As it can highlight the spatial variation in the use of land, this method of measuring had geographic value. The formula used for calculating cropping intensity is as follows:

$$CI = \frac{\text{Total cultivable area}}{\text{occupied area}} \times 100$$

To know the agricultural development during the recent years, the data for the years 2005-2006 and 2014-2015. The calculated percentages (cropping intensity) of these two years by wards and village tracts are presented in Table (10) and (11).

Table (10) Cropping Intensity within Bago Township in 2005-2006

No	Intensity	Number of Village Tract	Village Tracts
1	100-150	39	Zaungtu, Zeetaw, Tamarpim, Warpyangoun, Thayetgoun, Ahseiktaung, Thansotpin, Bounutgyi, Wingabaw, Thabayeyoe, Wunbeein, Ywarthikkainetar, Pyinbongyi, Paypinchaung Mokka, Kadwinchan, Zaingganainggyi, Maegoun, Layeinsu, Naungein, Ahlineni, Warmayan, Aukkabar, Sitpinseik, Hlawgar, Inntakaw, Bulaein, Tharyargoun, Lathargoun, Kautchair, Hamawlon, Hnyatyawtaw, Kyautan, Htanpinchaung, Phayanggautto, Htonegyi, Kanni, Kinpinechone, Tharyar Aye.
2	151-200	27	Kanmyint, Phayargyi, Phayarkalay, Pauktaw, Mayin, Shanywargyi, Ohbo, Shwetan, Latpankhon, Kamarnat, Sinete, Hmontine, Zayenaungpin, Ahtaksitee (E), Auksitee (E), Oukpho, Ahwine, Takkalay, Aktaksitee (W), Asksitee (W), Kyaikdoyyon, Kontaing, Htantaawgyi, Pyinmangy, Tarwa, Kwampaung, Lathar Aye.
3	More than 200	2	Latpanwin, Gweitanshay.
	Total	68	

Table (11) Cropping Intensity within Bago Township in 2014-2015

No	Intensity	Number of Village Tract	Village Tracts
1	100-150	39	Kanmyint, Ahseiktaung, Thabayeyoe, Wunbein, Oukpho, Naungein, Htantawgyi, Inntakaw, Kanni, Kinpinechone
2	151-200	45	Zaungtu, Zeetaw, Tamarpin, Warpyangoun, Thayetgoun, Thayetgoun, Thansopin, Bawuntgyi, Wingabaw, Phayarkalay, Pauktaw, Twarthikkainetar, Pyinbongyi, Mayin, Shanyeargyi, Paypinchaung, Latponkhon, Kamarnat, Mokkala, Sinete, Kadwinchan, Hmantine, Takkalay, Ahwine, Ahtaksitee(W), Auksitee (W), Auksitee (W), Zaingganainggyi, Moegoun, Layeinsu, Kyaikdayyon, Kontaing, Ahlineni, Warmayan, Aukkabar, Sitpinseik, Hlawgar, Pyinmangyi, Tharwa, Lathergoun, Hnyatpyawtaw, Kyauktan, Kwampong, Phayarnauto, Htenegy, Latar Aye, Thar Aye
3	More than 200	8	Phayarkalay, Shwetan, Ohbo, Zayenaungpin, Ahtaksitee (E), Auksitee (E), Latpanwin, Gweitanshay
	Total	68	

For the township as a whole, the cropping intensity in 2014-2015 was 129.56. The village tracts with high cropping intensity (200 and more) are Phayargyi. Shwetan, Paypinchaung, Zaynaumhpin, Ohbo, Ahtatsitee (E), Auksitee (E), Letpanwin and Gweitanshay. Generally these village tracts are close to water sources for growing in the dry season. However, Zaungtu, Zeetaw, Tamarpin, Aseiktaung, Thansopin, Thabayeyoe, Wunbein, Ywathit, Layeinsu, Naung- in, Ahlineni, Warmayan, Aukkabar, Sitpinseik, Hlawgar, Inntagaw, Bule-inn, Thayargone, Kautchair, Kanni and Kinpinechone village tracts are low in cropping intensity, more than 150, owing to inavailability of irrigation water in the dry period. Fig (11) and Fig (12).

Figure 11 Cropping Intensity within Bago Town Ship (2005-2006)

Figure 12 Cropping Intensity within Bago Town Ship (2005-2006)

Conclusion

Findings

The agriculture of Bago Township has notably increased in the 10-year period from 2005-2006 to 2014-2015, particularly in the problem of paddy and pulses. The increase in the paddy production was due to horizontal expansion of sown area and the introduction of summer paddy and also the use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and high yield varieties. Due to high demand of pulses, particularly green gram (pedisein) and matpe (black gram), by the foreign markets, the production of pulses increased more than 3-fold. However, productive potential still exists among the major crops in yield or marketability through the introduction of more improved varieties and the local adaptive research work.

Recommendation

The department concerned should systematically maintain the existing irrigation canals and establish more sources that can store the surplus water during the rainy season. Occasional education talk and discussion with farmers should be carried out to convey the scientific method of farming to the farmers. More high yield varieties suitable to the local conditions should be distributed through intensive research work, otherwise the development momentum of agriculture would be somewhat retarded in the foreseeable future.

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